

bcšn tkrd dFkrq i frfcahr gskkjs I kefnzd 0; ki kjß

Jh fot; cl lik d" Gh

i hpMh I ákškd

I kjk k %

i kphu dkGki kl w Hkkjrkr I epz 0; kikj dyk tkrks I epz 0; kikjps
oxoxG; k fBdk.kh mYysk feGr vl ys rjgh cšn tkrd xFkkru iek.kHkr o
fof'ol uh; ekfgrh feG.; kl enr gks tšB I kfgR; hd nqkz Hkkxor ; kP; k
erkuq kj tkrd dFkkph fufezh b-l -i wZ rhl js rs b-l -ukP; k nll js 'krd ; k
dky[kMkr >kyh v'kk tkrd dFkkP; k I gk; kus i kphu Hkkjrkrhy I kephd
0; kikj] 0; kikjkrhy oLrj 0; kikjh I žk ½Js kh½ i kphu Hkkjr; egRoi wZ canjž
0; kikjh ekxž nh'kkn'kd ; aks b- xkšVhøj izdk'k Vkdirk ; sks ; k tkrd dFkrq
ufou I ákšku i wZ ekfgrh izdk'kr vk.k.ks gk ; k I ákškukpk e[; gsrq vkgs

cht I žk %

tkrd] tafi] i] fu; ketē] fn'kkdkd] ckos -

i kLrkfod %

b-l -i wZ 486 e/; s Eg.ktp o; kP; k 80 0; k o"khZ xkšre cđnkps fu/ku
dqkhuxj ; šks >kys¹ R; kP; k eR; urj cšn /kekžk id kj FKkayk gskk- R; keGs

gk /keɪ dɪkj i pɔr gks ; kl kBh xks'e cɔnkp ; k f'k" ; kauh R ; kauh l kɔxryy ; k dFkkps
l ɔyhdj.k dsys R ; kykp tkrd dFkk vl s Eg.krkr-² ptkrdB Egt.ks xr
tUekrhy dFkk gks -³ ckSn /kekP ; k ekU ; rsud kj xks'e cɔnkauh 546 tUe ?ksrys o
iR ; d tUekr , d , d xqk feGowu R ; kauh cɔnRo iklr >kys l RrfiVdkrhy]
[kɔdfudk ; e/khy 15 0 ; k Hkkxkr ; kps l ɔydu dsys vkgs⁴

v'kk d'kkæ/kau ; skkU ; k iR ; {k o viR ; {k ekfgrhP ; k vk/kkjs ikphu
Hkkjrkry l kepnd 0 ; kikjoj iɔk'k Vdkrk ; sks

tkrd dFkrhy iɔk'k cɔjs %

ikphu Hkkjrkry l kepnd cɔjpk mYys[k oxoxG ; k xFkkru iR ; {k o
viR ; {kjhR ; k dsys ; k o.kukru feGr vl ys rjhgh ckSn tkrd dFkkæ/kau l ɔnk
; kps l folrj foj.k dsys vkgs v'kk tkrd dFkkæ/kau ikphu Hkkjrkry
cɔjpk ekfgrh feGr 'kɔ kj d]⁵ Hk : dPN]⁶ rkefyrh] l p.kkæh]⁷ [kɔekyh]⁸
vXxheky] n/kheky] oMxkoed]⁹ b- iɔk'k 0 ; kikjh cɔjpk mYys[k tkrd
dFkkæ/ ; s feGrks

l kepnd 0 ; kikjh ekxZ %

ikphu dkGki kl u Hkkjrkpk l epz 0 ; kikj ikgr vl rkuk iFke fl ɔkq l ɔk
rhrhy 0 ; kikj ikg.ks egRokps Bjrs ykFky ; Fkhy mR[kuuke/ ; s tgktkph xknh
feGkysyh vl u ; ko : u fl ɔkq l ɔk rhrhy ykd oxoxG ; k nskk kh l epz 0 ; kikj
djhr vl kor-¹⁰ ; k dkGkrhy l kepnd 0 ; kikjh ekxkpk vh ; kl dj . ; kl kBh
tkrd dFkkpk mi ; ksx gksks ; k cɔjpk mi ; ksx varxh o ijns kh ; 0 ; kikj
dj . ; kl kBh dsk tkr gsrk- Hkx'dPN ; k cɔjkekxZ l p.kkæhyk tkAu 0 ; kikj

djhr vl r- ; k ekxkzr vl yv; k rki jkcksz¹¹ ; k ns'kk'kh 0; ki kj dsyk t'kbZ ; kp
ekxkZus el gyhi VVu ikl q cakypk mi l kxj ikj djw i w dMhy }hi dYiky
tkr vl r- gk ekxZ l jG ; o}hi] l q.kZ}hi] p'ak o d'cksty k t'kMysy k gkrk- ; k
ekB; k l eqtr d'syach; k izdkjps t'gkt ykxr vl s¹²

l eqz 0; ki kj o fn'kkn'kZd ; a=s %

tkrd dFkkp; k vH; kl kruu jkpd o of'k"V; i w kZ ekfgrh feGrs i kphu
dkGkr foKku r'Kkukph izrh >kyh ul rh rjhgh l eqz 0; ki kj dj. ; kl kBh
fn'kkn'kZd ; a= Eg.kuu i {; k'pkk mi ; ksx dsyk t'kbZfn'kkdkdp¹³ %dkoGk½ P; k
enrhus i jns'kh; 0; ki kj dsyk tkr gkrk- ; k nh'kkdkdps of'k"V Eg.kts t'ks
eutq; oLrh vl y r'f'kp rks vki ys oLrhLFkku djrks ; k of'k"V; kpk Qk; nk
?ks'au i kphu Hkkjrh; 0; ki kU; k'uh i jns'kh; 0; ki kj dsyk- v'kk i {k'pkk fn'kkn'kZd
; a= Eg.kuu i kphu Hkkjrh; 0; ki kU; k'uh mi ; ksx dsyk- rj i-e-t'ks'kh ; k'p; k ers
l eqz 0; ki kl j djrkukR; 0; ki kU; k'adMs nh'kk ; a= vl s R; k fn'kk; a=dke/; s , d
y'k[k'ah ekl k r'kyr r'j'kr B'oyyk vl s o R; kps r'kM ugeh mRrj'adMs vl s¹⁴ ; k
osoxG; k l k'kukpk okij d: u l eqz 0; ki kj dsyk tkr gkrk-

0; ki kj hoLrq %

tkrd dFkkp; k ek/; ekruu i kphu Hkkj'rkrhy 0; ki kjh oLr'p j izd'k V'kdrk
; rks 0; ki kjh oLr'p/; s fofo/k izdkjps l q'rh dki M] gLrhna] el KY; kps i nkFkZ
v'kSk/kh ouLi rh] ekY; oku [kM\$ jRu\$ panu] dkl okph i kB] fofo/k l k'kj i k.kh b-
pk l eko'sk gkrks ckos tkrdke/; s fn'kkdkd'p okij fn'kk; a=d Eg.kuu djhr

vl rkukp gk i {kh ckWthyks¹⁵ i eP; k oGd ekjkpk 0; ki kj d: u rks 100
dk"kkā .kkyk fodyk¹⁶ v'kh jat di .kū ekfgrh feGrs

0; ki kjh Js kh %

ckSn tkrd dFKkP; k l gk; kus i kphu Hkkjrkrhy l enz 0; ki kjkcjkscjp
0; ki kjh Js khps Eg.ktp 0; ki kjh l ākkph ekfgrh feG.; kl enr gks vkiyk
0; ki kj 0; oLFkhr o l g {khr jhr; k i kj i km.; kl kBh l egkus 0; ki kj dsk tkbz
Js khP; k i edkkyk bJSBh¹⁷ Eg.kr- JSBhP; k funž kkuđ kj l āwkZ l enz i dkg dsk
tkr gkrk- v'kk 0; ki kjh Js khps dkgh fu; e vl r- rs fu; e ekM. kKŪ; kl Js khru
ckgj dk<ys tkr- vkiY; k 0; ki kjkrū feG.kKŪ; k uŋ; krū dkgh jDde
l ektki ; kxh dkekd kBh nku nr vl Y; kps mYyŋk feGrkr¹⁸

eW; eki u %

Hkkjr gk e/; orhZ 0; ki kjkps dnz Eg.kū i fl /n gkrk- Js khP; k ek/; ekru
0; ki kjh ngP; k inskk r tkĀu 0; ki kj djr gks l ākVhr i .ks dsk; k 0; ki kjkrū
Hkkjrh; 0; ki kjh /ku/kKŪ; kus l e/n >kys brdp uŋs rj vkiY; krhy dkgh
jDde /kkfeZdkekd kBh nku nr vl Y; keGgs Hkkjrkr 'ksy LFkki R; kph] efinjkph o
okLrph fufeZh gks; kl enr >kyh- ik-Hkkjrkrhy 0; ki kjkrhy ixrh eGp
e/; dkGkrhy okLrph fufeZh >kyh- i kphu Hkkjr kP; k vkfFKZd LFK\$ kā kBh
0; ki kjkrhy ixrh gs egRokps dkj.k gks - 0; ki kŪ; kauh l enz 0; ki kj djhr
vl rkuk l ākVhri .ks gk 0; ki kj dŋ; kps fnl rs vl k 0; ki kj gkr vl rkuk
l ākVhri .ks gk 0; ki kj dŋ; kps fnl rs vl k 0; ki kj gkr vl rkuk dkgh oGd
u\$ fxkd l dVkoj ekr djhr l ŋk: i i .ks vkiY; k 0; ki kjkr ok< dŋ; kph fnl rs

vl k 0; kikj gkr vl rkuk dkgh oGd uš fxzd l dVkoj ekr djhr l qk: i i .ks
vkiY; k 0; kikjkr ok< dY; kph fnl rs gk 0; kikj djhr vl rkuk ososxG; k
oLrP; k 0; kikjkrw ekB; k iæk.kkr Qk; nk feGfor vl r-

I nHkZ xfk

- 1- MKWkkxor nqkZ [kM Ø- 4 i: Ø- 442
- 2- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 1 i: 136
- 3- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 1 i: 136
- 4- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 4 i: 145
- 5- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 4 i: 117
- 6- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 4 i: 13
- 7- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 4 i: 13
- 8- JhokLro cyjke] Trade and Commerce in ancient India, i: Ø-109
- 9- mijkDr] [kM Ø-60
- 10- Jh on0; kl] i: Ø-202
- 11- i- tkskh egknø 'kkL=h] ejkBh fo'odksk] [kM 6 i: Ø-98
- 12- JhokLr cyjke] Trade and Commerce in ancient India, i: Ø-108
- 13- MKWkkxor nqkZ [kM Ø-3] i: Ø-103-
- 14- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 3 i: 103
- 15- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 3 i: 103
- 16- fdRrk] [kM Ø- 3 i: 103
- 17- MKW kSukbZduojš xk; dokM] i kphu o e-Hkjrkpk brhgkl] i:60
- 18- mijkDr] [kM 4 i:13